

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LINGUOSTYLISTIC MEANS OF CREATING AN IMAGE

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Abstract

The paper deals with the ways of creating an image in a literary text. Different stylistic means are described, classified and categorized in order to show the variety of the possibilities of the image creation. The author highlights the most widely spread means of creating an image and shows why they are more widely used. The conditions of the author's choice of the means of expressiveness are also touched upon in the paper.

Keywords: linguistics, image, means of expressiveness, stylistic devices, phraseology, expressive connotation, context.

Images of a clear, objective world create a special object of philological studies. Speaking about the concept of "an image", we abstract it from a particular canvas of a work of art. And of course, the most random and insignificant phenomena, details in the art world are a way to characterize a person and express his individuality. This also includes the concept of the "world of things", introduced by A. B. Esin.[1]

So, a picture similar to our world, which includes people, things, actions, nature, etc. makes up an image. And all such images are united in the concept - an artistic detail, the smallest expressive and pictorial detail that develops into a "block" of a larger image, which in turn flows into an even larger image - a holistic image. Summing up, we can assert that material concreteness forms an integral, essential facet of objective figurativeness in fiction.

Expressive means are usually called rhetorical figures - i.e. stylistic terms used for greater expressiveness of speech. The purpose of such stylistic figures is to make our speech more colorful, richer, in other words, to attract attention and awaken the emotions of the reader. Our speech is arranged in such a way that when it meets all the norms, it is less expressive. On the contrary, when incompatible concepts are combined, a certain veiled thought appears, and such a turnover is filled with a new original meaning.

It happens so that in the presence of numerous phraseological units, the language "hardens", and all original forms turn into clichés, losing all their expressiveness. In this case, many authors try to "revive" expressiveness by modifying phraseological units.

Let us pay attention to the most widely used tropes: epithet, metaphor, figurative comparison, hyperbole, personification. Epithet - (epitheton Greek - application) is a figurative definition of a phenomenon, object, action. Epithets, in turn, can be classified from several positions. From the point of view of semantics: natural, household, color, zoomorphic, intensifying, contrasting. They are subdivided into: individual-author's, general language, folk-poetic. According to structure - simple, complex. By belonging to parts of speech: epithets-nouns, epithets-adjectives, epithets-adverbs.

In addition, epithets can be divided according to the type of transfer and from the position of its presence: metaphorical, metonymic, exact. The syntactic function also plays a leading role. So, an epithet can be a subject in a sentence, a definition, an object. Metaphor - (Greek - figurative meaning) the use of a language unit in a figurative sense, the transfer of signs of one phenomenon, inherent only to it, to another, due to any similarity of these phenomena. The peculiarity of the metaphor lies in the fact that it depicts a comparison, the parts of which have merged so much that the first part (the one that is compared) is displaced and completely replaced by the second (the one with which it is compared). [2]

A metaphor is also called an abbreviated simile. It always concatenates two values at the same time. The first meaning, which determines the context, and the other - determined by the usual meaning of the word, i.e. meaning out of context. The main feature of metaphor is similarity. The image and the object are combined in one word so that the word has several meanings at once: figurative and direct. The figurative meaning is the image, the direct meaning is the object itself. And

there must be similarities between them. Metaphor is one of the most common types of tropes, because the similarity between phenomena and objects can be based on the most variable features. Depending on the approach to typology, there are several types of metaphors. A figurative comparison is a stylistic device based on the partial similarity of several objects of reality, but belonging to different groups, classes, types. Compared objects do not have a complete identity, but only resemble each other, which gives a new idea of an object or phenomenon. Their combination or attribute, on the basis of which a partial identity is formed, is called the basis of comparison, which allows for the abstraction of comparison, i.e. a property that is inherent in the compared objects.

Hyperbole (or exaggeration) focuses attention on any sign, emphasizes it. In most cases, hyperbole is used to convey a certain drama, sentimentality and sensitivity. Attribution and properties of the living to the inanimate. Human nature is very inclined to look for

something alive and human in many things and phenomena, as if looking for harmony and understanding in everything that surrounds it, which is probably why this technique is so well perceived by the reader.

An artistic portrait is a rather complex phenomenon that does not have a single interpretation. Therefore, the creation of a character is not only the endowment of character traits, the narration of his feelings and thoughts, this is a way to make the reader see individuality in the hero. One of the most common ways to create an image is a portrait of a character, that is, a description of his appearance, facial features, figure. More often, demeanor, gestures, facial expressions, and so on are associated with appearance.

But the portrait description of the hero may be absent, and then the reader receives basic information about the character from his actions, thoughts and feelings, speech. Appearance can tell a lot about the hero - age, nationality, social status, tastes, habits. L.A. Yurkina claims that the portrait of a character consists of three main features:

1. natural features;
2. features characterizing the hero as a social phenomenon;
3. facial expression.

She also believes that the correspondence between the inner and the outer allows the writer to use the appearance to create a certain generalized image, in other words, such a hero becomes the embodiment of some property or some trait of human nature. [2]

The portrait of a character can be considered both in a narrow and in a broad sense. In a narrow sense, a verbal portrait is a continuous descriptive chain, no more than one sentence. In a broad sense, a portrait is a collection of all descriptive chains dedicated to one hero.

Following such conclusions, one can single out a compact verbal artistic portrait and a dispersed one. Compact is distinguished by a single portrait description, having described the character's appearance once, the author may not return to it. A dispersed verbal portrait is a periodic reference to the external data of the hero in the course of the narration of the work. A verbal artistic portrait is quite multifunctional and can perform various functions within a work of art in accordance with the functional fullness of the text. The orientation of the text (philosophical, social, religious, and so on) is reflected in the portrait, making it an important compositional element of a work of art. Each writer, using a portrait as a technique for creating an artistic image, pursues a specific goal, therefore, a portrait description will also have a specific function. For example, the evaluation function will help the reader to understand the nature of the character and contribute to the disclosure of the ideological and artistic meaning of the work. In turn, the aesthetic function will help to express the connection between form and content, without which there will be no artistic image. All others pass through the aesthetic function, which is its systematizing property. This means that in its pure form, the aesthetic function does not exist. [3]

Taking into account all of the above, the verbal portrait of the hero is an important method of revealing

the intention of the literary text and contributes to a deeper understanding of the personality of the character. Also, the methods of creating an image can be: characterization, monologue, dialogue, interior and so on. A characteristic is a way of describing a character, phenomenon or event in a work of art. It directly expresses someone's vision of the situation. But this component is more descriptive, and therefore is used sporadically. Quite a lot of attention in the work of art is given to the speech of the hero. The manner of speech can tell a lot about the character himself.

In its turn, speech can be internal and direct (dialogue or monologue). A monologue is one of the ways of expressing the feelings and thoughts of the author or character, it can be the author's or the character's monologue. This type of speech not only characterizes the character, but also more fully reveals his feelings, attitude towards himself or other characters. The image of the hero is easier to identify in his monologue. But one of the significant drawbacks of the monologue is the slowdown in the dynamics of the plot. No action is expected during the monologue, and the reader may lose the plot thread. Monologues should be used in the same way as a characterization - episodically. Dialogue is a method of expressing thoughts through the conversation of characters (two or more). Dialogue, unlike monologue, gives the action dynamism. But, just like in a monologue, the characters are characterized and revealed to the reader as individuals. Through dialogue, the author's perception of the characters is also indirectly expressed. However, dialogues have the same property as monologues - they distract from the main plot. Repetition plays an important role in creating an image. Repetitions are used not only to characterize the hero, but also determine the points of contact between the heroes. Each character is depicted independently, but one is presented as a reflection of the other. For this effect, repeating verbs, adjectives in greater frequency are used; nouns, repetitions of remarks, comparisons of characters in a smaller one. The coincidence of signs and actions of different heroes of the work have their own motives and manifestations. Both characters can be in the same situation, do the same things, evaluate the third character, but the train of thought and the final reaction of both can be either similar or directly opposite. [4]

Descriptive devices such as interior and landscape are also very often used. Interior - the word comes from the French language (fr. Interieur), in literature it is an artistic description of the interior decoration of a room. It can also characterize the hero, create an atmosphere, contributing to the disclosure of the author's idea. The interior and portrait are closely related to the aspect of artistic detail, in other words, a small detail can become the main feature of the image. Often it is through such a detail that the key characteristics of the hero are transmitted. The interior can show what significant changes have occurred to the hero over a certain period of narrative time. Landscape - also has its origin in French, the view of the area. Landscape is a type of artistic description, the main subject being described in which is nature or an architectural complex, a city. In literature, the landscape is one of the main means of revealing the

author's idea. He also obeys literary trends (romantic landscape, naturalistic, symbolic), genres (urban, rural, marine) and the goals of the writer (disclosure of the hero's state, contrasting landscape and human nature). [5]

The landscape can become the starting point or the main object of the author's intention, embodying the thoughts and philosophy of the author and the person. Based on all of the above, the artistic techniques for creating the image of a character include: portrait, characterization of the author, speech, interior and landscape, where the portrait of the hero and landscape occupy a dominant position. Some conclusions should be drawn on the chapter as a whole. Image and figurativeness are the dominant concepts, both in the work of art itself and in the literary language. Without them there is no literary art itself. And to create imagery, various

techniques and methods are used: Linguistic and artistic, which in turn have several subclassifications. Obviously, the choice of means and the model for constructing an image completely depends on the intention and idea of the author.

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